

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part XI. Condensation of Benzeneazo- β -diketones with Phenylhydrazine

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Several 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-, 1,5-diphenyl-3-methyl-, and 1,3,5-triphenyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles have been synthesised and their characteristics are described.

Interest in the chemotherapeutic activity of certain pyrazole derivatives has led to the synthesis of some of them by the condensations of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds with phenylhydrazines (Garg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 948). In the present communication the behaviour of benzeneazo derivatives of acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, and dibenzoylmethane with phenylhydrazine has been investigated.

4-Benzeneazopyrazoles (II) have been found to be formed; intermediate dihydrazones could not be isolated (cf. Beyer and Claisen, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 1697).

Substituted benzeneazopyrazoles are highly coloured substance, varying in colour from yellow to red. These are soluble in acetic acid, ethanol, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL**

The synthesis of benzeneazo derivatives were effected by the action of benzenediazonium salts on β -diketones (Garg, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 626).

1-Phenyl-3, 5-dimethyl-4-benzeneazopyrazole.—A solution of benzeneazoacetylacetone (0.01M) in ethanol (15 c.c.) and phenylhydrazine (0.01M) in glacial acetic acid were heated on a water bath for 4 hours. On cooling and dilution with water, a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from ethanol gave 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-benzeneazopyrazole.

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**Melting points are uncorrected.

Characteristics of different 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

1-Phenyl-3-5-dimethyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles.

No.	R*.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Phenyl	78%	62°	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄	N : 19.94	20.28
2.	4-Methoxyphenyl	72	85°	Pale yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₄	N : 18.08	18.30
3.	4-Bromophenyl	79	136°	Light yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ Br	Br: 22.24	22.53
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	79	109°	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 11.11	11.43
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	73	56°	Light yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 11.08	11.43
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	71	107°	Orange-red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 11.18	11.43
7.	4-Nitrophenyl	81	140°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₅	N : 21.62	21.80
8.	3-Nitrophenyl	80	112°	Brownish red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₅	N : 21.56	21.80
9.	2-Nitro-4-chlorophenyl	80	122°	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 9.58	9.98

*Vide structure (II; R' = R'' = Me).

1,5-Diphenyl-3-methyl-4-benzeneazopyrazole was prepared from benzeneazobenzoylacetone and isolated in the same manner as above. Characteristics of different 1,5-diphenyl-3-methyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

1, 5-Diphenyl-3-methyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles.

No.	R*.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Phenyl	80%	136°	Golden yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄	N : 16.32	16.56
2.	4-Methoxyphenyl	74	104°	Yellow	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ON ₄	N : 15.04	15.21
3.	4-Bromophenyl	82	106°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ Br	Br: 18.62	19.18
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	81	120°	Pale yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.14	9.53
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	80	96°	Golden yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.21	9.53
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	80	122°	Orange-red	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.11	9.53
7.	4-Methylphenyl	68	117°	Orange	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄	N : 15.61	15.90
8.	3-Methylphenyl	62	84°	„	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄	N : 15.56	15.90
9.	2-Nitro-4-chlorophenyl	81	102°	„	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 8.21	8.50

*Vide structure (II; R' = Ph; R'' = Me).

1, 3, 5-Triphenyl-4-benzeneazopyrazole.—A solution of benzeneazodibenzoyl-methane (0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and phenylhydrazine (0.01M) were heated on a water bath for 3 hours. On dilution, a crystalline precipitate was obtained, which was recrystallised from acetic acid. Characteristics of different 1,3,5-triphenyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles are described in Table III.

TABLE III

Characteristics of 1,3,5-triphenyl-4-benzeneazopyrazoles.

No.	R*	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Phenyl	80%	156°	Orange-red	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄	N : 13.81	14.00
2.	4-Methoxyphenyl	74	136°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ ON ₄	N : 12.84	13.02
3.	4-Bromophenyl	82	162°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ Br	Br : 16.34	16.70
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	81	152°	Orange-red	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.01	8.16
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	80	122°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 7.82	8.16
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	80	125°	Orange-red	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 7.84	8.16
7.	4-Nitrophenyl	84	147°	Orange-red	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₅	N : 15.61	15.73
8.	3-Nitrophenyl	81	140°	Orange	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₅	N : 15.52	15.73
9.	2-Nitro-4-chlorophenyl	83	104°	Dull red	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 7.12	7.40

*Vide structure (II: R' = R'' = Ph).

The author is indebted to Dr. S. S. Joshi, Principal, Meerut College, Meerut, for his keen interest in this investigation. He is also thankful to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for a research scholarship.

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Received April 22, 1961.